

Effect of Leadership Style, Work Environment, Work Motivation and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance SMAN 3 Solok Selatan

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study is to see how (1) Leadership Style affects employee performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan. (2)The impact of the work environment on SMAN 3 Solok Selatan employees' performance. (3) Employee performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan is influenced by work motivation. (4) The impact of employee satisfaction on performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan (5) At SMAN 3 Solok Selatan, job satisfaction, work environment, work motivation, and job satisfaction all have an impact on employee performance. This study's population consists of all 70 employees of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan. Total sampling is a technique for determining the number of samples. Multiple regression was utilized in the data analysis technique because it met the requirements of the classical assumption test of normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity. The findings of this study show that (1) leadership style has a beneficial impact on the performance of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan personnel. (2)The work environment has a beneficial impact on the performance of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan staff. (3)Work motivation has a favorable impact on the performance of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan employees. (4) Employees of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan's job happiness has a favorable impact on their performance. (5) Leadership style, work atmosphere, work motivation, and job satisfaction all have a favorable impact on SMAN 3 Solok Selatan employees' performance.

Keywords:- Performance; Leadership Style; Work Environment; Work Motivation; Job Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the government sector, human resources play a critical and strategic role in achieving organizational objectives. This is because, even when infrastructure and other resources are sufficient, humans become planners, actors, and determinants of the achievement of the organization's goals. As a result, in order for organizational tasks to be carried out effectively, efficiently, and optimally in the government environment, it is necessary to develop planned and sustainable human resources that will provide competent, professional human resources capable of high-quality performance in accordance with the organization's demands.

Established in 1991, State Senior High School (SMAN) 3 Solok Selatan is one of the senior high schools in

South Solok Regency. SMA Negeri Lubuk Gadang was the name of the high school when it first opened, and it was housed in the SD Negeri 01 Lubuk Gadang building. There were 125 alumni in the initial class. This SMAN has achieved so much along the way that the regent of South Solok was named the favorite SMAN in the South Solok Regency in 2005. From 2006 until the present, this school has been appointed as the organizer of the Superior Class of the South Solok Regency.

However, the school's performance of both teachers and staff has deteriorated during the last two years. For the period 2019 to 2020, Table 1.1 highlights the performance achievements of programs/activities carried out by workers of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan. From the statistics in Table I, it can be seen that staff performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan has dropped from 2019 to 2020. SMAN 3 Solok Selatan employees' average performance In 2020, it was 75.03 percent, down from 73.39 percent the previous year. Low efficiency As a result of this employee, SMAN 3 Solok Selatan's objective and mission are more difficult to achieve.

No	Respondent	Average Performance Score per Individual	
		2019	2020
1	Respondent 1	77.40	76.56
2	Respondent 2	76.25	78.40
3	Respondent 3	78.04	77.65
4	Respondent 4	68.41	66.28
5	Respondent 5	68.41	70.24
6	Respondent 6	75.25	73.46
7	Respondent 7	78.21	80.62
8	Respondent 8	80.30	76.27
9	Respondent 9	72.40	73.21
10	Respondent 10	79.20	77.61
	Average	75.39	75.03

Table 1: The Average Performance Value of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan Employees

Source: Administration of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan

Leadership, work environment, work motivation, and job satisfaction are regarded to be factors in employee underperformance. This is also in line with Hessel's (2007: 178) opinion, according to which discipline, work environment, motivation, job satisfaction, compensation, leadership, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment are all elements that might affect organizational success.

Leadership is the most significant aspect of management, as it plays a crucial and strategic role in a company's survival. According to Rivai (2011), leadership is the practice of influencing or setting an example for one's followers through communication in order to attain organizational goals.

The work environment is another aspect that influences employee performance. As the parent company, the organization must establish a pleasant and conducive work atmosphere that encourages people to perform efficiently. Providing a pleasant work atmosphere will allow employees to be satisfied with their work and will leave a lasting impact on them, resulting in good performance and, of course, the ability to enhance their performance (Ginanjar, 2013: 2).

According to Kreitner and Kinicki, work motivation has an impact on performance (2001:205) Workplace motivation can have an impact on performance, but it isn't the sole thing that influences it. The importance of superiors' work motivation in improving employee performance cannot be overstated. Motivation is a driving force that encourages people to do things in order to achieve their goals.

Job satisfaction is another aspect that might have an impact on performance. According to Gibson (2020:110), the reciprocal relationship between job satisfaction and performance is thoroughly demonstrated. On the one hand, it is said that job satisfaction leads to increased performance, implying that happy employees are more productive.

As a result of the phenomena mentioned by the researchers above, researchers are interested in performing additional research on the performance of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan, by identifying and examining numerous elements that affect employee performance.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The population is a generalization area made up of objects/subjects with specific attributes and characteristics that researchers have chosen to study and derive conclusions from (Sugiyono, 2014: 115). The population of this study included all workers (teachers and staff) of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan, a total of 70 people. The sample is a representation of the population's size and features. Sugiyono (2014), p. 116. To use a total sampling technique or a population sample to determine the sample in this study. The participants in this study were all employees of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan, which included up to 70 people.

Multiple regression analysis was employed in this work to test hypotheses. The goal of multiple regression analysis is to figure out what causes the influencing variables to effect the affected variables. The following is an example of a multiple regression equation model:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + b_4 X_4 + e \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

- Where:
- Y = Performance
 - a = Intercept Constant
 - X1 = Leadership Style
 - X2 = Work Environment
 - X3 = Motivation
 - X4 = Job Satisfaction
 - b1, b2, bn. = Regression Coefficient
 - e = Error Term

III. RESULT

A. Classic assumption test

a) Normality test

This normality test is used by the author to ensure that the regression model is normal. The kolmogorov-smirnov test method is used to test each variable. The regression model is regularly distributed if the Kolmogorov-Smirnov sign for each variable is greater than 0.05. The results of the normality test are shown in Table II;

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test						
		Y	X1	X2	X3	X4
N		70	70	70	70	70
Normal Parameters	mean	41.2262	44.7143	44.8095	43.9643	42.2262
	Std. Deviation	2.34059	3.64236	1.83327	2.52909	2.34059
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.116	.112	.206	.161	.116
	Positive	.110	.112	.206	.161	.110
	negative	-.116	-.085	-.175	-.125	-.116
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1,453	1,299	1,628	1,066	1,027
asympt. Sig. (2-tailed)		.921	.648	.283	.467	.738

Table 2: Normality Test Results

Sumber: SPSS output results, 2021

The confounding or residual variables in the regression model have a normal distribution, as shown in Table 2, which is a normality test. The performance variable (Y) has a sig value of 0.921 > 0.05, the leadership style variable (X1) has a sig value of 0.648 > 0.05, the work environment variable (X2) has a sig value of 0.283 > 0.05, the work motivation variable (X3) has a sig value of 0.467 > 0.05, and the job satisfaction variable (X4) has a sig value of 0.738 > 0.05. As a result, the performance, leadership style, work environment, motivation, and job satisfaction variables of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan personnel can be determined to be regularly distributed.

b) Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test can be used to see if the regression model discovered a relationship between the independent variables. If the independent variables are correlated, the regression model is not good; if the independent variables are correlated, the variables are not orthogonal. Orthogonal variables are independent variables with a correlation value of 0 between them (Ghozali, 2011). Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor show multicollinearity (VIF). Look at the Tolerance and VIF values of each independent variable to see if there is a

divergence from the multicollinearity test; if the Tolerance value > 0.10 and the VIF value 10, the data is free of multicollinearity symptoms, as shown in Table III.

Coefficientsa			
		Collinearity Statistics	
Model		Tolerance	VIF
1	Leadership Style	.484	2,067
	Work environment	.406	2,463
	Work motivation	.405	2,472
	Job satisfaction	.487	2.053

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Table 3: Multicollinearity Test Results

Source: SPSS output results, 2021

It is clear from the multicollinearity test in the table above that the independent variables have no relationship. As a result, there are no issues with multicollinearity in this research model.

c) Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test is used to see if there is an inequality in variance in the residuals from one observation to the next in a regression model. Homokedastability occurs when the variance between the residuals of one observation and the residuals of another observation is constant, while heteroscedasticity occurs when the variance is different. The Plott Graph (Scatter Plot) test was employed in this investigation to detect the presence of heteroscedasticity. There is no heteroscedasticity if there is no discernible pattern, such as points scattered above and below the number 0 (zero) on the Y axis. Figure 1 shows the outcomes of the tests.

Fig. 1: Heteroscedasticity Test Results

The points are distributed above and below the number 0 on the Y axis in the image above, indicating that there is no discernible pattern. This demonstrates that the data in this study is not heteroscedastic.

d) Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The magnitude of the effect of the independent factors on the dependent variable is determined using this method. A multiple regression equation can be used to calculate the amount of the influence of independent factors

on the dependent variable. Using the IBM SPSS for Windows Version 24.0 application, computer computations were performed.

The findings of the regression coefficient value, tcount, significance value, F count value, and R Square (R²) value are summarized in the table below. Table 4 summarizes the findings.

The regression equation model for the influence of leadership style, work environment, work motivation, and job satisfaction on employee performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan, as shown in table 4, is as follows:

$$Y = 34,563 + 0.215 (X1) + 0.277 (X2) + 0.553 (X3) + 0.345 (X4)$$

Coefficientsa						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	34,563	6.084		5.681	.000
	X1	.215	.052	.020	4.117	.000
	X2	.277	.078	.246	3.534	.012
	X3	.553	.092	.165	5,995	.000
	X4	.345	.106	.049	4.427	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Table 4: Recap of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Results

Source: Primary Data, Processed with IBM SPSS 24.0 2021

Explanation of the above equation:

a= 34,563; it means that the employee's performance is worth 34,563 units without the influence of leadership style, work environment, work motivation, or job happiness.

b1= 0.215; suggests that there is a positive influence on performance from leadership style characteristics (X1) (Y). This demonstrates that improving employee performance requires a higher (excellent) or rising leadership style. Leadership style has a regression coefficient of 0.215, which means that for every one-unit increase in leadership style, employee performance rises by 0.215 units.

b2= 0.277; It means that work environment variables (X2) have a beneficial impact on performance (Y). This demonstrates that the better the workplace, the better the employee's performance. The work environment regression coefficient is 0.277, which means that for every one-unit increase in work environment, the employee's performance improves by 0.277 units..

b3= 0.553; means that the variables of work motivation (X3) have a beneficial impact on

performance (Y). This demonstrates that increasing or increasing employee motivation improves employee performance. The work motivation regression coefficient is 0.553, which means that for every one-unit increase in work motivation, the employee's performance improves by 0.553 units.

b4= 0.345; indicates that job satisfaction characteristics (X4) have a beneficial impact on performance (Y). This demonstrates that increasing employee work happiness improves staff performance. The job satisfaction regression coefficient is 0.345, which means that for every one-unit improvement in job satisfaction, the employee's performance improves by 0.345 units.

B. Statistic Test

a) Hypothesis Testing 1

The first hypothesis is that leadership style has a moderately beneficial impact on employee performance. The significance level of the leadership style variable is 0,000 of the significance value, according to the results of the t test study (0.05). As a result, Ho gets rejected whereas Ha is accepted. As a result, the alternative hypothesis suggested in this study is accepted, implying that leadership style has a considerable impact on staff performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan.

b) Hypothesis Testing 2

The second hypothesis is that the workplace has a partially favorable impact on employee performance. The significant level of the work environment variable is 0,012 of the significance value, according to the findings of the analysis of the t test (0.05). As a result, Ho gets rejected whereas Ha is accepted. As a result, the alternative hypothesis suggested in this study is accepted, implying that the work environment has a considerable favorable impact on the performance of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan employees.

c) Hypothesis Testing 3

Work motivation has a partially favorable effect on performance, according to the third hypothesis provided. The significant level of the work motivation variable is 0,000 of the significance value, according to the results of the analysis of the t test (0.05). As a result, Ho gets rejected whereas Ha is accepted. As a result, the alternative hypothesis suggested in this study is accepted, implying that work motivation has a considerable impact on employee performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan.

d) Hypothesis Testing 4

The third hypothesis proposed is that job satisfaction partially has a positive effect on performance. Based on the results of the analysis of the t test, it is known that the significance level of the job satisfaction variable is 0,000 < dai significance value (0.05). Thus Ho is Job satisfaction has a partly positive effect on performance, according to the fourth hypothesis given. The significance level of the job satisfaction variable is known to be 0,000 dai significance value based on the findings of the study of the t test (0.05).

As a result, Ho gets rejected whereas Ha is accepted. As a result, the alternative hypothesis suggested in this study is accepted, implying that job happiness has a considerable impact on SMAN 3 Solok Selatan employees' performance..

Table 5 summarizes the findings of evaluating the first, second, third, and fourth hypotheses.

Hypothesis	Statement	Test results
H1	Leadership style has a significant effect on employee performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan.	Accepted
H2	Work environment significant effect on employee performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan.	Accepted
H3	Work motivation significant effect on employee performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan.	Accepted
H4	Job satisfaction significant effect on employee performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan.	Accepted

Table 5: Summary of Partial Hypothesis Testing Results

Source: Primary Data, Processed by the Author in 2021.

C. F test (simultaneous)

a) Hypothesis Testing 5

The F test (model feasibility) is used to simultaneously analyze the effect of the independent factors on the dependent variable (all at once). Employee performance is improved by a mix of leadership style, work environment, motivation, and job happiness, according to the fifth hypothesis. According to the findings of the F test analysis, the significant level of the variables of leadership style, work environment, work motivation, and job satisfaction is 0.000 0.05. As a result, Ho is turned down, whereas Ha is approved. So that the alternative hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted, leadership style, work environment, work motivation, and job satisfaction all have a significant impact on SMAN 3 Solok Selatan personnel's performance. The results are shown in Table 6.

ANOVA ^b					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	27,143	4	9.048	8,632	.000a
Residual	271,632	65	7.545		
Total	298,775	69			

a. Predictors: (Constant), X4, X2, X1, X3
 b. Dependent Variable: Y

Table 6: F Test Results

Source: SPSS Output Results (year 2021)

The summary results of testing the fifth hypothesis can be shown in table VII.

Hypothesis	Statement	Test results
H5	Leadership style, work environment, work motivation and job satisfaction together have a significant effect on employee performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan	Accepted

Table 7: F Test Results

Source: Primary Data, Processed by the Author in 2021.

D. Coefficient of Determination Testing (R2)

Analysis of leadership style, work environment, work motivation, and job satisfaction coefficients of determining The IBM SPSS for Windows Version 24.0 application is used to analyze employee performance, with the SPSS output form given below:

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.611a	.373	.311	2.26374

Table 8: R Square Test Results

Source: Primary Data, Processed with IBM SPSS 24.0 2021. Appendix 7

The adjusted coefficient of determination, or R Square, is 0.373, indicating that 37.3 percent of the variation in all independent variables (leadership style, work environment, work motivation, and job satisfaction) can be explained by the dependent variable (employee performance), with the remaining 63.7 percent explained by variables not studied in this study.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Following are some conclusions that can be derived from the test results:

- The leadership style of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan personnel has a beneficial impact on their performance. This means that if the agency's leadership style is good, it will be able to inspire people to improve their performance.
- The work environment has a beneficial impact on the performance of SMAN 3 Solok Selatan staff. This means that a positive work environment can boost employee morale and help them perform better. The better an employee's work environment at an agency, the better his performance in carrying out his duties in the agency.
- Employees at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan perform better when they are motivated at work. This suggests that if an employee's work motivation is high for the agency, the person will be excited and capable of doing well. High performance will be aided by this positive work drive.
- Employees at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan have a beneficial impact on their performance due to job satisfaction. This indicates that if staff are satisfied with their jobs at the agency, they are more motivated and capable of doing a good job. Strong performance will be aided by high job satisfaction.

- Leadership style, work environment, work motivation, and job satisfaction all have a positive impact on employee performance at SMAN 3 Solok Selatan. With a F ANOVA test number of 0.000, the independent variables of leadership style, work environment, work motivation, and job satisfaction influence employee performance.

Based on the results of the discussion analysis and certain conclusions in this study, the following are some suggestions that can be made based on the study's findings in order to achieve better results:

- The agency's management is expected to improve the agency's leadership style, work atmosphere, work motivation, and job satisfaction. Because higher productivity and attainment of agency goals necessitates a change in leadership style, work atmosphere, motivation, and job happiness. When leadership style, work atmosphere, work motivation, and job happiness are all balanced, employee performance improves.
- Future researchers should be able to look at other variables except this one in order to get more varied results that can define what factors affect performance, and it is suggested that research on the influence of leadership style, work environment, motivation, and satisfaction be expanded. In this study, work on employee performance was applied.

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